

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Rakhmankulova Bibinora Khushbak kizi¹

¹Termez State Pedagogical Institute,

Foreign Language and Literature: English Language, master

Uralova Oysulov Poyan kizi²

²Termez State Pedagogical Institute, Phd.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7461007>

Abstract.

The article discusses the importance of using new pedagogical methods in physical education classes and the advantages of physical education classes in the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: education, ethics, physical education, style, methodology, student, athlete.

INTRODUCTION

Sports opportunity. Sport is the most effective way to introduce a country to the world. A combination of sports, beauty, honesty and health. Most of the opportunities created in our country are dedicated to sports. Taking into account that the highest results are given to sports competitions before the Science Olympiads, we teachers have a huge task to popularize science among young people and to deliver sports champions. In the course of the article, we want to talk about the methods that are effectively used to achieve such a good result.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Here, while paying attention to some textbooks, we come across information about the methods used in physical education. In particular, examples of methods are presented in the textbooks "Theory and Methodology of Physical Education" by R.S.Salomov, A.K.Sharipov and "Theory and Methodology of Physical Education" by S.R.Salomov. For example, in the textbook, while talking about the method of visualization, the following information is given about the method. It is noted that this method is widely used in physical education. That is, by affecting all the senses, communication with existing things is established. It uses sight, movement and other senses. These methods are divided into the following groups using a set of methods based on the characteristics of the exercises and performance conditions in the implementation of demonstration in a broad sense. They consist of methodical demonstration by the teacher or with the help of a student.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In order to form initial ideas about the effect of movement and the rules of performing the exercises, auxiliary means of demonstration, i.e. the direct demonstration method, are widely used. Such direct demonstration methods are divided into:

- display of pictures, diagrams, photographs and similar visual aids; Demonstration of product models and layouts;
- Movie and VCR show;
- Selected - using devices, for example: microphone,
- radio equipment, electric light signals;
- Directed sensory movement methods (for example, exercises);
- Orientation (goal) methods (hanging balls, flags, signs in halls and grounds, etc.).
- Leader and daily sensor planned methods;

- Quick information method (VCR).

We will fully analyze the essence of sports through the following story. "Compared to others, Sunnatillo's upbringing is a bit more difficult. After his father left for another woman, negative characters began to appear in his upbringing.

He was gripped by the idea that everything in life is taken by force.

As a result, he used his physical abilities instead of his mind. One day he tried to steal. Violence, theft, and adultery became normal for him. In doing so, he took advantage of the opportunities he gained by training his physical strength a little.

The physical education teacher noticed these changes of Sunnatillo, who was studying with excellent grades. And to turn the young man away from this path, he used a special method." The fact that Sunnatillo had already entered this street, these habits were absorbed into his blood, made it difficult to change him. But this method of the pedagogue helped him a lot. Method's first plan encouraged him verbally, that is, Sunnatillo's favorite sport is wrestling, and he said that to achieve great success in football, he only needs to practice, and he hopes that he will become a great athlete in the future. After the first victory, Sunnatillo started training. Despite the fact that he took all his pains from sports, his teacher told him that sports is a friendship, a door of opportunities, a beginning of kindness. His victories in sports and the support of his teacher changed him in a positive direction. Now he has become a breadwinner who takes care of his brothers and supports his mother.

Yes, compared to other subjects, teaching methods in physical education classes are fundamentally different. In the process of physical education, the main activity of the teacher is carried out with words: with the help of words, knowledge is imparted, understanding is activated and deepened, tasks are assigned, their execution is controlled, results are analyzed and evaluated, children are disciplined. The word solves the necessary task in understanding, evaluating and self-managing the activities of those involved.

In addition, the word consists of one or another dedicative story, conversation, discussion, etc., depending on its use.

The word method: 1) giving instructions; 2) additional explanation; 3) instructions and orders; 4) oral assessment; 5) self-talk and self-command; 6) encouragement, 7) verbal abuse; 8) general order; 9) analysis; 10) Verbal interaction In addition, giving instructions is also one of the effective methods. In this case, conveying concrete and clearly understandable rules for performing tasks or exercises to those involved in the technique learning activity.

In the additional explanation method, some actions or methods of execution are interpreted and explained through various exhibitions in order to provide deeper knowledge in order to improve the quality of the execution method.

Management of students' activities in the form of special words in instructions and commands. Pre-showing through instructions and commands is used to define tasks and is one of the most effective methods.

CONCLUSION

Sport, which unites the countries of the world with the ideals of friendship, health, honesty, kindness, is not only a science, but a vital necessity of physical education teachers. Sport is the most advanced way to introduce a country to the world. Skilled pedagogues certainly have their contribution behind the achievements of our boys and girls who are raising the flag of the country to the blue on this field today at international, world and Asian sports competitions. Recognizing this, the head of our country, who opens the door to more

opportunities and awards the most valuable prizes, has high hopes for us sports masters. Therefore, if we introduce new methods in the field and expand the ranks of world-class champions, we will be able to create great opportunities in the implementation of great tasks.

References:

- 1.X. Raxmankulov, B. Jurayev. "Biznes va tadbirkorlik sirlari". Tashkent- 2002.
- 2.A. Ulmasov. Bozor iqtisodiyoti. Qisqacha lug'at – ma'lumotnoma. Toshkent-1991.
- 3.S. Nosirxujayev. Siyosatshunoslik fani bo'yicha qisqacha lug'at – ma'lumotnoma. Toshkent. "O'qituvchi".
- 4.Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English, A.S. Hornby. – London: Oxford University Press, 1998.
- 5.The Random Dictionary of the English Language: The Unabridged Edition. – New York: Random House, 1997.
- 6.[www.http:qomus.info>oz/encyclopedia/i/ibora/](http://qomus.info>oz/encyclopedia/i/ibora/)

